

Bridging Realities: Advancing Modular Construction through BIM and Mixed Reality Integration

ANKITA MAURYA

Supervisors:

Bruno Figueiredo

School of Architecture, Art and Design, University of Minho, Guimarães, Portugal

Filipe J.S Brandao

School of Architecture, Art and Design, University of Minho, Guimarães, Portugal

Pedro Andrade

Grupo CASAIS, Braga, Portugal

Abstract

Compliance checks play a crucial role in the process of building permitting as it ensures the quality of the designs of building submitted for construction. In addition to being the most important step in the process, it is also the most complicated one as it involves great technical expertise to thoroughly check all the details in the drawings and models against the standard regulations. Although most of the steps in the building permitting process is digitalised and automated, the compliance checking process is manual, in most countries, which makes the process time taking and exhausting for the experts, creating a need for the automation. Some studies have developed BIM-integrated compliance checking methods in the past few years, which are utilised in some parts of the world, but the need for a framework that is accessible and interoperable is still present. The work in this dissertation follows a mixed approach research methodology to automate the compliance checking process with the integration of open BIM standards like IFC (Industry Foundation Classes) and IDS (Information Delivery Specification).

With the incorporation of theoretical study and practical application, the dissertation aims to design and develop a workflow to check the information of IFC files against the general regulations of building standards. The aim is to provide an efficient and practical solution for regulatory compliance checking in the process of building design and permitting. To analyse the effectiveness and limitations of the developed framework, it is demonstrated on a real-world scenario with the general regulations and project prototype in the context of Nepal. The results indicate its practical adaptability along with some challenges providing opportunity for future advancements.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/5SHrEr4r5oQ>

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